

Communication Patterns and User Characteristics on Business Platforms: The Case of XING

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<https://wissensbank.info/SOCIAL-MEDIA/Social-Media-Charaktere>)

Abstract

Social networks such as XING and LinkedIn are playing an increasingly important role in the professional context, particularly as communication, marketing and sales tools. Despite the availability of sociodemographic data, there is still little empirically sound knowledge about the typical behavioral patterns of users of such platforms in the context of social media events. This article presents the results of an empirical study conducted with 150 XING users by means of standardized interviews. Four prototypical user groups were identified: "Fast Sellers," "Business Contactors," "Event Hoppers," and "Partner Surfers." These characters differ in their motivations, communication styles, and networking skills and often have an tense relationship with each other. The study contributes to the typification of social media users in a business environment and provides starting points for further research.

1. Introduction

Business platforms such as XING and LinkedIn are becoming increasingly important for maintaining business contacts and as marketing and event organization tools. This raises the central question of which user groups engage on these platforms and how their communication behavior is structured. So far, the scientific debate has primarily focused on sociodemographic characteristics (see Neuberger & Langenohl, 2019; Wellbrock & König, 2022), while insights into specific usage habits, particularly in the context of live events, are lacking. This paper addresses this by identifying and classifying typical user types.

2. Theoretical background

Business networks can be described as hybrid platforms that enable both digital and analog interactions (Krotz & Hepp, 2018). While LinkedIn operates globally, XING focuses primarily on German-speaking countries. There are a variety of motivations for using the platform, ranging from professional to private interests. Research discusses networking (Ellison et al., 2007), self-presentation (Meier, 2020) and the constitution of social capital (Putnam, 2000) as central functions. However, a systematic typology of users of social business platforms is still lacking.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research design

In the period from January to August 2015, standardized interviews were conducted with 150 randomly selected platform users as part of several XING events. The aim was to identify recurring characteristics of social media users and to systematize them on the basis of typical behavior patterns.

3.2 Data collection

As moderator of a XING group with over 5,000 members, the author had direct access to potential interview partners. The questionnaire included sociodemographic data (age,

gender, education, income) and, in particular, questions about usage behavior and motivation. The answers were dichotomous (yes/no). A pre-test was carried out before the main survey to ensure the validity and comprehensibility of the items.

4. Results

The analysis of the interviews allowed the respondents to be differentiated into four characteristic groups, which are outlined below (see also Figure 1).

It is noteworthy that many users switch between professional and private group affiliation, depending on the type of event. In addition, a tension dynamic between the groups emerged: for example, business networkers often reject fast salespeople as “dubious,” while event hoppers and partner surfers are avoided by business-oriented users.

One key finding concerns network competence: business networkers and fast salespeople are significantly more networked than the other groups, both on the platform itself and in the context of personal interactions.

SOCIAL MEDIA - CHARACTERS					
[Hermann, A.-J. (2015) / Revision 2022]					
		Persona A	Persona B	Persona C	Persona D
		Fast Seller	Business Executive	Event Hopper	Partner Surfer
Personas (Description)	Behavior: Transaction-oriented communication with a focus on short-term business deals; assertive demeanor; focus on monetary objectives.	Behavior: Long-term network management; professional and strategic relationship management; focus on mutual business added value.	Behavior: Participation in events primarily for social or entertainment purposes; no specific business objective; informal communication.	Behavior: Privately motivated contact; use of the platform to initiate personal relationships; focus on interpersonal exchange.	
	Self-interest and calculating benefits are strongly pronounced. They want simple, immediate business deals and quick profits.	Business contacts are characterized by efficiency orientation, a sense of status and a pronounced claim to leadership. They have an intellectual character, are professionally and socially established and open to innovative solutions.	The event hopper is not primarily defined by professional status or academic background. Rather, it is a mixed group - from ordinary employees to civil servants and pensioners.	Partner surfers are generally singles who are specifically looking for partnerships or friendships without resorting to traditional dating platforms.	
Demographic classification	In many cases, the fast salesperson changes sectors repeatedly or runs several vendor's tray businesses at the same time.	Their responsible actions prevent them from instrumentalizing social contacts for short-term transactions. Instead, they pursue a sustainable networking strategy.	Event hoppers do not use the platform for explicitly professional purposes, but to maintain private contacts, for networking out of personal interest or to participate in events without any strategic business connection.	This user group is characterized by the indirect search for interpersonal relationships via business portals. They often prefer this approach as it allows them to make contacts without being immediately categorized as single or looking for someone.	
	Everyday life is characterized by fear of the future and few opportunities for advancement.				
		Fast salespeople are often people who are not necessarily academically trained or hold traditional management positions.	Business contacts have predominantly medium to higher educational qualifications and are often employed in managerial or qualified positions.	Predominantly intermediate educational qualifications (e.g. secondary school leaving certificate, advanced technical college entrance qualification) and basic professional qualifications.	The majority of partner surfers have an intermediate level of education or professional qualifications. There is no discernible concentration of academically highly qualified users within this group.
		Average income: € 30,000 - 50,000 gross/year, sometimes fluctuating strongly, commission-based.	As a rule, they have a medium to high income: approx. 50,000 - 80,000 € gross/year.	Rather stable income (employees, civil servants, pensioners), rarely high: approx. 30,000 - 45,000 € gross/year.	The income level is between € 35,000 and € 50,000 gross per year.

Source: Hermann, A.-J. (2016/Revision 2022)

5. Discussion

The study provides initial empirically based evidence that users of business platforms can be categorized into clearly distinguishable character types. This typology not only opens up perspectives for the further development of communication science theories on digital network formation, but also provides practical implications for the event and community management of business platforms.

It should be noted, however, that the study only examined XING users in German-speaking countries and that the results can only be applied to other platforms to a limited extent. Further research could be conducted to make cross-platform and international comparisons.

6. Conclusion

The present study has provided a first systematic approach to characterizing social media users on business platforms. The differentiation into four prototypical groups forms a basis for future research in the field of professional communication, network building and digital socialization. However, an empirical study of the research subject in the sense of a theoretically sound and systematic analysis could not be provided.

Based on this, the question of how many people can be assigned to the four groups was not relevant to this research process. Nevertheless, the result makes it clear which groups of people are substantially active in business networks. However, further research is needed to test the theoretical approaches and the method used. In this context, a sufficiently large, representative sample should also be taken.

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